

Ultra-high speed fabrication of TiO₂ photoanode by flash light for dye-sensitized solar cell

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Abstract

In this work, a new way to fabricate nanoporous TiO₂ photoanode by flash light is demonstrated. TiO₂ nanoparticles are sintered on FTO glass by flash light irradiation at room temperature in ambient condition, which is dramatically simplified, ultrahigh speed and one-shot large area fabrication process compared to a conventional high temperature (450~500 °C) thermal sintering process. The effect of the flash light conditions (flash light energy and pulse numbers) on the nanostructures of sintered TiO₂ layer, was studied and discussed using several microscopic and spectroscopic characterization techniques such as XRD, SEM, AFM and UV-vis. The sintered TiO₂ photo anodes by flash light were used in DSSC and its performance were compared with that of DSSC fabricated by conventional thermal sintering process. It was found that a flash light sintered TiO₂ photoanode has efficiency which is similar to that of the thermal sintered photoanode. It is expected that the newly developed flash light sintering technique of TiO₂ nanoparticles would be a strong alternative to realize the room temperature and in-situ sintering of photoanode fabrication for outdoor solar cell fabrication.

Keywords: *Dye-sensitized solar cell (DSSC), Flash light (IPL), TiO₂*

1. Introduction

Recently, dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSC) has received increased attention as they are a low-cost alternative to conventional silicon based solar cells owing to potentially high efficiency(~10%) and low cost fabrication processes. Furthermore, DSSCs are applicable to windows or wearable electronic products due to their transparency and flexibility.

Conventionally, nanoporous TiO₂ photoanode is fabricated through blading or screen printing of TiO₂ slurry followed by high temperature (450~500 °C) thermal sintering. However, high temperature processes include fatal problem.

Lowering the processing temperature is required for cell fabrication on flexible substrates.

Recently, laser sintering process of TiO₂ have been widely studied to alleviate this problem. However its application to mass production is difficult as a laser sintering process can cover only a small sintering area and it requires a sophisticated 3D-gantry system to cover a large area. Therefore, new low temperature and large area sintering technique has been required. In this letter, we report a room temperature, ambient condition and ultra-high speed process to fabricate TiO₂ photoanode for dye-sensitized solar cell (DSSC) applicable to mass- production.

Fig.1. Schematic of DSSC

2. Experimental procedure

The TiO₂ thin-film electrode was designed and fabricated for use in the dye-sensitized solar cell. This TiO₂ thin-film was deposited on the surface of a FTO glass (Fluorine doped tin oxide, SnO₂:F) substrate, of dimensions 50 x 50 x 2.2 mm and a sheet resistance of 7 Ω/sq. And then the working electrode with the layer of TiO₂ nanoparticles was sintered at 500 °C for 30 min in a high-temperature furnace. And a FTO glass substrate with a layer of TiO₂ nanoparticles was then kept immersed for 24 h at room temperature in a mixture containing a solution of N-719 dye (Ruthenium 535-bis TBA) and distilled water. Using these procedures a conventional working electrode with a layer of thermal sintered TiO₂ nanocrystalline was compared with the working electrodes with the layer of TiO₂ nanoparticles sintered by flash light (IPL : Intense Pulsed Light) with different IPL conditions (Table 1) for the aim of demonstrating the feasibility and advantages of the DSSC by IPL sintering. Having prepared the working electrode, the counter electrode was prepared by depositing a thin film of platinum on the FTO glass substrate. The two electrodes were fitted together and sealed by melting sheet (SX 1170-60, 60 microns thick), such that there was a space between the two electrodes which was adjusted to approximately 50 μm for insertion the liquid electrolyte. After sealing, the liquid electrolyte, Iodide based redox electrolyte (Iodolyte AN-50), was injected into the cell through a hole on the cell that was prepared in advance.

A digital sourcemeter (Keithley 2611A) was utilized to measure the open-circuit photovoltage and short-circuit photocurrent of the DSSC. A solar simulator (Abet technologies, LS150) with 150W xenon arc lamp source was employed to illuminate the DSSC on the condition of 1.5 AM.

To obtain high performances comparable to conventional DSSC by thermal sintering, we performed experiments for optimizing IPL sintering DSSC in different conditions in this study as shown in Table 1. The parameters of IPL sintering are irradiation energy per unit area, pulse number, on time/off time and shot number.

(a)

(b)

Fig.2. (a) Schematic of IPL sintering
(b) Pulse management of IPL

Pulse number	3	10	50
10 J (4 shot)	2ms/10 ms	4.3ms/10ms	6.8ms/10ms
20 J (4 shot)	2ms / 30ms	2 ms / 30ms	2 ms/ 30 ms
30 J (4 shot)	1.5ms/30ms	1.5ms/30ms	1.5ms/30ms

Table 1. Test conditions of IPL sintering

From the study, we found out that IPL sintering is possible with certain conditions (20 J/cm², 3 pulse, on/off time 2 ms / 30 ms, 4 shot). The effect of the flash light conditions (flash light energy and pulse numbers) on the nanostructures of sintered TiO₂ layer, was studied and discussed using several microscopic and spectroscopic characterization techniques such as SEM, AFM, XRD and UV-vis. And we compared performance of DSSC fabricated by IPL sintering with that of DSSC fabricated by conventional thermal sintering process through I-V curve.

3. Results and discussion

Figure 3 shows scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrographs of IPL sintered TiO₂ nanoparticles on glass under different IPL condition : (a) pure TiO₂ , (b) IPL irradiated TiO₂ with 20J -3pulse. In 20J -3pulse condition, we can confirm that fine grains were formed comparing

pure TiO₂. That means there are some changes in TiO₂ nanoparticles as irradiated by flash light. As the results of manufacturing solar cells and measuring efficiency, IPL sintering of TiO₂ is possible in 20J -3pulse condition. Thus we could think the SEM image (Fig. 3(b)) means the result of IPL sintering. However we couldn't logically prove IPL sintering of TiO₂ is possible in 20J -3pulse condition. So we also take AFM (Atomic Force Microscope) images to compare pure TiO₂, thermal sintered TiO₂ and IPL sintered TiO₂ with different irradiation energy conditions. Figure 4 shows pure TiO₂ changes similar to thermal sintered one as IPL irradiation energy increases. That means IPL sintering of TiO₂ is possible and sintering-degree of TiO₂ grow up as IPL irradiation energy increases. However, through manufacturing solar cells and measuring efficiency, we confirmed that IPL sintering of TiO₂ isn't efficiently accomplished as irradiation energy simply increases.

Fig.3. The SEM (scanning electron microscopy) image of TiO₂ ; (a) pure TiO₂ , (b) 20J -3pulse

Fig.4. The AFM image of TiO₂ (a) pure TiO₂, (b) 20J -3pulse, (c) 30J -3 pulse,
(d) Thermal sintering

Figure 5 shows the J-V characteristics for several DSSCs containing the results of measuring efficiency of the DSSCs. As the results, DSSC with flash light sintering process (20 J/cm², 3 pulse, on/off time 2 ms / 30 ms, 4 shot) has almost half of efficiency of DSSC with thermal sintering process.

So we sintered the whole area of TiO₂ layer through twice irradiation of flash light. And then DSSC with two-step flash light sintering process in same condition has efficiency similar to that of DSSC with thermal sintering process. In IPL sintered DSSC, the short circuit current density (J_{sc}) is 0.786mA/cm² nearly same to thermal sintered one,

0.839mA/cm². Also, the open circuit voltage (V_{OC}) doesn't largely different between IPL and thermal sintered DSSCs. In conclusion, the IPL sintered DSSC has almost same efficiency with conventionally thermal sintered DSSC. It is expected that DSSC with flash light process would have high performance by changing flash light condition; irradiation energy per unit area, pulse number, on time/off time and shot number. Varying these parameters, we will be able to achieve higher efficiency of IPL sintered DSSC and epoch-making in solar cell study field.

4. Conclusion

In some IPL condition, IPL sintering of TiO₂ is possible and IPL sintered DSSC has almost same efficiency with thermal sintered one. Therefore, it is expected that IPL sintering process would be used efficiently to commercial dye-sensitized solar cells and would be a solution for the low-cost and mass production of high performance DSSC is possible. Based on the flash light sintering process proposed in this study, high performance DSSC working electrode can be fabricated in short time (msec) at room temperature and in ambient condition.

Fig.5. A comparison I-V curve of DSSC by IPL sintering with that of DSSC by thermal sintering

Therefore, it would realize the solar painting process where the solar cell can be directly fabricated on the window and wall in real time. Through the solar painting process, low cost installation of the DSSC can be realized.

References

- [1] Morio Nagata, Mutsumi Kimura, and Minoru Taya "Design of dye-sensitized solar cells with new light-harvesting dyes", *Proc. of SPIE*, Vol. 6927, 692718, 2008.
- [2] Heng Pan, Seung Hwan Ko, Nipun Misra, and Costas P. Grigoropoulos "Laser annealed composite titanium dioxide electrodes for dye-sensitized solar cells on glass and plastics", *Applied physics letters*, Vol. 94, 071117, 2009.
- [3] B. O' Regan and M. Gratzel "A low-cost, high-efficiency solar cell based on dye-sensitized colloidal TiO₂ films", *Nature*, Vol. 353, 737, 1991.
- [4] Yasuo Chiba, Ashraf Islam, Ryoichi Komiya, Naoki Koide, and Liyuan Han "Conversion efficiency of 10.8% by a dye-sensitized solar cell using a TiO₂ electrode with high haze", *Applied Physics letters*, Vol. 88, 223505, 2006.
- [5] S. Nakade, M. Matsuda, S. Kambe, Y. Saito, T. Kitamura, T. Sakata, Y. Wada, H. Mori and S. Yanagida "Dependence of TiO₂ nanoparticle preparation methods and annealing temperature on the efficiency of DSSCs", *J. Phys. Chem. B*, Vol. 106, 10004, 2002.
- [6] Sukwon Jung and Jung Hyeun Kim "Sintering characteristics of TiO₂ nanoparticles by microwave processing", *Korean J. Chem. Eng.*, Vol. 27, 645, 2010.

Sample	J_{SC} (mA)	V_{OC} (V)	FF (%)	η (%)
20 J - 3	0.394	0.347	39.8	0.054
20 J - 3 (two step)	0.786	0.340	38.8	0.104
Thermal	0.839	0.362	40.2	0.12